

Gas chromatograms of molecular extracts from WBPH-resistant Rathu Heenati and susceptible TN1 rice plants. IRRRI, 1988.

250 °C, at 5 °C per min. One μ l of the extracts was used for analysis on the splitless mode.

The figure shows qualitative and quantitative differences between molecular distillate extracts of resistant Rathu Heenati and susceptible TN1. This may reflect different volatile composition of the odors produced by rice plants that influence the insect locating its host plant. □

Ptb 10 — a promising donor of gall midge (GM) resistance

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During the 1986 rainy season a severe epidemic of GM in Srikakulam District destroyed resistant varieties Phalgun and Surekha (derivatives of Siam 29). Grain yield losses were estimated at 50-

Reaction of donors and derivatives to GM. A.P., India, 1988.

Designation	Parentage	GM incidence ^a (% SS)			
		30 DT		50 DT	
		HB	TB	HB	TB
Ptb 10	Donor	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil
Ptb 18	Donor	20	1.45	20	2.07
Ptb 21	Donor	40	4.26	40	4.36
Ptb 33	Donor	20	2.18	20	3.67
Siam 29	Donor	45	4.93	100	24.52
Leuang 152	Donor	45	6.51	100	29.56
OB677	Donor	30	2.97	30	3.20
Phalgun	IR8/Siam 29	90	22.25	95	40.99
Surekha	IR8/Siam 29	65	7.31	100	49.07
Jaya (susceptible check)	TN1/IR8	70	9.16	90	32.69

^aHB = hill basis, TB = tiller basis.

90%. We evaluated certain potential new donors of resistance to the GM population of the district during 1988 rainy season at Panukuvalasa, a hot spot location.

Seven proven donors and two derivatives of Siam 29 were planted in six rows of 16 hills each at 15- × 15-cm spacing. GM incidence was recorded at 30 and 50 d after transplanting (DT) on hills and tillers from 20 preselected hills/entry.

Among the Ptb series, only Ptb 10 had no silvershoots (SS) (see table). The

three other donors had 20-40% SS/hill at 50 DT.

Phalgun and Surekha, the predominant varieties of the north coastal district of A.P., had 95-100% SS/hill and 41-49%/ tiller at 50 DT. Susceptible check Jaya had 90 and 33%, respectively. Proven donors Siam 29 and Leuang 152 had 100% GM/hill and 24-30%/ tiller.

These results show the need to reorient the breeding programs for GM resistance, using Ptb 10 as one of the donors. □

Excess water tolerance

Changes in shoot growth in response to partial submergence

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We tested tall and semitall rice varieties for growth and yield under normal and semideep water (55-60 cm) in a tank experiment during 1980 wet season (kharif). Seedlings (30-d-old) were transplanted in two tanks, with three replications. At 25 d after transplanting, one tank was flooded to 55-60 cm water depth, the other was kept at 5-10 cm. Plants were sampled at 20 and 45 d after submergence, flowering, and maturity.

At 20 d after submergence, 55-60 cm water reduced dry weight 23% and leaf area per tiller 58%. At flowering, they increased 41 and 26%, respectively (see table). Excess water significantly increased dry weight/ tiller at maturity. In almost all varieties, specific leaf weight (SLW) increased significantly at 20 d after submergence. Crop growth rate under 55-60 cm water was reduced by 50% 20-45 d after submergence, but increased during pre-anthesis (45 d after submergence to flowering) and post-anthesis (flowering to maturity).

Semitall Jagannath showed drastic reduction in shoot growth under 55-60 cm water, Janaki and CR1030 (tall) had maximum stability. □

Morphological changes in rice shoot due to excess water.^a Cuttack, India, 1980 wet season.

Variety	Treatment	Dry weight/tiller (g)			Leaf area/tiller (cm ²)		Specific leaf wt (mg/cm ²)		Crop growth rate (g/m ² per d)		
		20 DAS	Flowering	Maturity	20 DAS	Flowering	20 DAS	Flowering	20-45 DAS	45 DAS to flowering	Flowering to maturity
Janaki	Normal	0.76	2	4.30	75.3	41	2.70	7	5.6	11.6	4.0
	Submerged	0.72	3	4.43	52.8	101	5.43	6	5.8	12.8	4.2
CR1030	Normal	0.76	3	4.96	91.8	73	3.25	7	10.1	12.1	4.5
	Submerged	0.79	4	5.96	57.6	90	5.23	7	8.4	14.4	3.2
FR13-A	Normal	0.78	2	4.47	84.6	60	4.35	7	7.2	11.6	3.6
	Submerged	0.80	3	6.43	52.6	65	5.03	7	4.6	16.6	2.9
CN643	Normal	0.46	2	3.57	78.0	61	2.54	6	4.5	3.3	1.1
	Submerged	3.35	3	6.14	18.6	68	4.53	6	3.8	6.0	6.5
IET6205	Normal	0.73	2	5.67	96.3	56	2.93	7	8.8	6.9	3.6
	Submerged	0.53	4	7.20	45.8	94	4.56	8	7.7	12.5	5.8
IET6207	Normal	0.74	3	4.60	100.0	72	2.98	7	7.0	8.8	5.3
	Submerged	0.42	4	4.74	31.5	78	4.83	8	6.3	6.8	6.4
CR260-131	Normal	0.68	3	5.32	103.3	101	2.68	7	9.2	12.3	1.8
	Submerged	0.36	4	6.56	24.8	94	4.20	7	0.8	15.3	1.1
Mahsuri	Normal	0.59	1	3.33	81.4	40	2.60	6	10.6	1.4	9.9
	Submerged	0.64	4	3.73	52.2	90	4.90	7	1.1	11.0	8.1
IET6271	Normal	0.59	3	3.80	91.2	68	2.68	6	8.2	9.2	1.2
	Submerged	0.33	3	4.30	24.4	64	4.46	6	2.3	6.0	2.7
Jagannath	Normal	0.60	2	2.90	85.3	55	2.90	6	8.2	9.7	2.4
	Submerged	0.25	2	3.75	15.1	44	3.70	6	0.3	4.8	3.0
Mean	Normal	0.67	2	4.15	88.7	63	2.87	7	8.0	8.7	3.7
	Submerged	0.51	4	5.42	37.6	79	4.70	7	4.1	10.6	5.0
LSD (0.05)	Treatment	0.05	0.1	0.50	5.0	6	0.29	ns	1.2	1.4	1.0
	Variety	0.11	1.0	1.03	11.2	12	ns	1	2.7	3.2	1.5
	T×V	0.16	1.8	1.45	15.9	18	ns	ns	ns	4.5	ns

^aDAS = days after submergence.

Adverse soils tolerance

A rapid screening technique for salt tolerance in rice

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We screened 34 rice varieties for salt tolerance at germination and at the seedling stage. The effects of level of salinity and stage of salinization on rice growth were studied separately.

For seedling stage screening, 14-d-old seedlings were transplanted to Yoshida nutrient solution salinized incrementally with NaCl to concentrations of 0, 50, 100, 150, and 200 mol for 2 wk. Fresh and dry weight and percentage mortality were the criteria for assessing tolerance. The experiment was repeated with 16

varieties and with 7 varieties selected out of the 16.

Results of the solution culture studies were compared with those of soil culture

in pots (nine varieties). The solution culture technique was fairly reliable; the patterns of salt tolerance in various varieties, especially for the most tolerant and most sensitive, were the same in pot culture and in the field (see table).

Fresh and dry shoot weights were compared after 2 wk in solution. The

Salt tolerance of rice varieties at different growth stages.^a Faisalabad, Pakistan.

Variety or line	Germination	Salt-tolerance rating					Final
		Seedling stage ^b experiment			Maturity ^c		
		I	II	III	Pot trial	Field trial	
Basmati 370	MS	S	S	S	S	S	S
Basmati 198	MS	MS	MS	MS	MT	S	MS
NIAB6	T	T	T	T	T	T	T
IR6	T	MT	MT	T	MT	T	T
KS282	T	MT	MS	MT	MT	T	T
BG402-4	MT	T	T	MT	S	S	MS
IR1561	S	S	S	S	S	S	S

^a Tolerance class: S = sensitive, MS = moderately sensitive, MT = moderately tolerant, T = tolerant

^b Fresh and dry shoot weight and % maturity. ^c Yield basis.

solution technique had a significant correlation among the three experiments, showing high consistency and reproducibility of the technique.

Similarity with the results with pot culture and close association with field results (where absolute yields were the indices of salt tolerance) show the

practical validity of this technique.

The technique is simple, quick, and reliable for screening a large number of genotypes. □

Relationship of rice embryo weight and salinity tolerance at seedling stage

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We screened 19 indica and 6 japonica cultivars with varying embryo weights for salt tolerance, using water culture in the IRRI phytotron glasshouse (29/21 °C (day/ night) temperature, 70% relative humidity, natural daylight). Salinity stress of 6800 ppm (EC 12 dS/m) was introduced by adding 1:1 mixture of NaCl and CaCl₂ to the nutrient solution. Seedling survival after 2 wk salinization was taken as the criterion for salt tolerance.

Embryo weight/50 seeds ranged from 0.0140 g (Intan Gawri and Palman 46)

Correlation ($r = 0.2151^{ns}$) between embryo weight and seedling survival after 14 d salinization (EC = 12 dS/m). IRRI, 1989.

Cultivar	Embryo weight (g)	Survival (%)
Rikuto Norin 15	0.0467	7
Bombilla	0.0454	36
Chang You Zae Rae	0.0450	10
Thatnosubnet	0.0440	12
Jinbu 4	0.0393	45
Pokkali	0.0386	85
Nona Bokra	0.0358	89
IR51491-AC4-6	0.0309	90
IR31779-19-3-3-2-2	0.0302	10
RNR1429	0.0299	18
IR51491-AC4-7	0.0297	82
IR51500-AC9-8	0.0272	32
TNAU (AD) 103	0.0263	8
MI-48	0.0245	2
Khao youth	0.0237	22
IR25924-92-1-3	0.0236	5
Laxmi	0.0227	8
IR28	0.0226	20
Suweon 341	0.0219	70
IR36	0.0209	42
NIAB6	0.0208	25
Duansan	0.0202	18
Basmati 370	0.0195	20
Intan Gawri	0.0140	8
Palman 46	0.0140	2

to 0.0467 g (Rikuto Norin 15). Seedling survival under salinity stress ranged from 2 (Palman 46) to 90 (IR51491-AC4-6).

Among the cultivars studied, the

association between embryo weight and salt tolerance was not significant ($r = 0.2151$) (see table). This finding does not support earlier reports of such an association. □

Ion transport in two rice varieties grown under saline conditions

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Resistance to salt entry into the shoot is often related to survival and growth of plant species. We studied the transport of Na⁺, K⁺, and Cl⁻ from root to shoot in two rice varieties with different salt tolerances.

NIAB6 (salt tolerant) and IR1561 (salt sensitive) were transplanted at 14 d after seeding into Yoshida nutrient solution. Two salinity levels (0 and 100 mol NaCl) were used. Samples were taken at 7, 14, and 28 d after salinization. Cell sap of whole shoot and root was analyzed and rate of ion transport calculated as

$$J = (M_2 - M_1) / (\overline{WR} \times \Delta T)$$

where M_1 and M_2 are amounts of ion in samples 1 and 2, respectively; $\overline{WR}$ is the log mean root fresh weight (g); and T is difference between harvests, in days.

Rate of Na⁺ transport from root to shoot increased with salinity during both growth periods, but was higher 14 d after salinization (see table).

IR1561 had four times higher Na⁺ transport rate (J_{Na^+}) than NIAB6.

J_{K^+} decreased considerably from 14 to 28 d under no salinity and under 100 mol salinity. At 100 mol salinity, the drop in K⁺ transport (J_{K^+}) in salt-sensitive IR1561 was spectacular.

Rate of ion transport from root to shoot in 2 rice varieties under 2 salinity levels (0 [control] and 100 mol NaCl). Faisalabad, Pakistan.

Variety	7-14 d		14-28 d	
	0 (control)	100	0 (control)	100
<i>Rate of Na⁺ transport (μmol/g dry wt per d)</i>				
NIAB6	6.0	26.1	2.2	23.7
IR1561	9.2	106.1	1.7	17.9
<i>Rate of K⁺ transport (μmol/g dry wt per d)</i>				
NIAB6	235.4	98.7	80.2	45.3
IR1561	325.4	193.2	78.1	5.9
<i>Rate of Cl⁻ transport (μmol/g dry wt per d)</i>				
NIAB6	30.1	76.6	15.3	26.8
IR1561	37.1	170.2	16.4	33.9

IR1561 had higher J_{K^+} during early stress, but could not maintain the rate of K⁺ transport.

J_{Cl^-} was also much lower for NIAB6 than for IR1561, particularly during the first growth period. It decreased substantially during the second growth period, although it was still higher for IR1561 than for NIAB6. Lower J_{Cl^-} for NIAB6 at high salinity at 14 and 28 d after treatment indicates it has a better Cl⁻ exclusion mechanism.

Zinc:phosphorus ratio — a criterion for salt tolerance in rice

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Different physiological parameters (potassium selectivity [K:Na ratio], exclusion/ inclusion of Na⁺ and Cl⁻ in